

Figure 5A: P-S6 Film

P-S6

Figure 5A Arrows indicate lanes used in figure

Lane 1: Sib-1 Veh, Lane 2: Sib-1 MK-2206 (30 nM), Lane 3: I-ASD-1 Veh, Lane 4: I-ASD-1 MK2206 (30nM)

Lane 5: Sib-1 Veh, Lane 6: Sib-1: SC-79 (2ug/mL), Lane 7: I-ASD-1 Veh, Lane 8: I-ASD-1 SC-79 (2ug/mL)

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Figure 5A: GAPDH for P-S6 (TOP)
GAPDH for Total S6 (Bottom)

10 wells

3, 15, 18

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Lane 1: Sib-1 Veh, Lane 2: Sib-1 MK-2206 (30 nM), Lane 3: I-ASD-1 Veh, Lane 4: I-ASD-1 MK2206 (30nM)
Lane 5: Sib-1 Veh, Lane 6: Sib-1: SC-79 (2ug/mL), Lane 7: I-ASD-1 Veh, Lane 8: I-ASD-1 SC-79 (2ug/mL)

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Figure 5A Arrows indicate lanes used in figure

Lane 1: Sib-1 Veh, Lane 2: Sib-1 MK-2206 (30 nM), Lane 3: I-ASD-1 Veh, Lane 4: I-ASD-1 MK2206 (30nM)
Lane 5: Sib-1 Veh, Lane 6: Sib-1: SC-79 (2ug/mL), Lane 7: I-ASD-1 Veh, Lane 8: I-ASD-1 SC-79 (2ug/mL)

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

AKK
1249 →

Figure 5A

Arrows indicate lanes used in figure

Lane 1: Sib-1 Veh, Lane 2: Sib-1 MK-2206 (30 nM),
Lane 3: I-ASD-1 Veh, Lane 4: I-ASD-1 MK2206 (30nM)
Lane 5: Sib-1 Veh, Lane 6: Sib-1: SC-79 (2ug/mL),
Lane 7: I-ASD-1 Veh, Lane 8: I-ASD-1 SC-79 (2ug/mL)
Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Total
AKK